

(porosity G_4). Wash the precipitate with hot water and finally with 5% ethanol to remove the excess of reagent. Dry at 110° to a constant weight and weigh as $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{ONS})_3$. The factor for Rh is 0.2140.

Thiophene-2-aldoxime has been reported⁸ to precipitate palladium(II) quantitatively at pH 0.2-0.8. It has also been found in this laboratory that osmium(VIII) is precipitated by this reagent at a pH < 2. Further, platinum(II) is not precipitated by the reagent. Separation of Rh(III) from Pt, Pd and Os was therefore studied. From a mixture containing Pd(II) and Rh(III), palladium was precipitated by the reagent at pH 0.2-0.8. The precipitate, after digestion, was filtered and washed with hot water. The filtrate and the washings containing Rh(III) were collected carefully and concentrated to about 100 ml. Rh(III) was then precipitated by addition of more reagent and raising the pH to 10.5-11.0. Estimation of rhodium was completed as described above. Pd(II) precipitate was weighed as $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{ONS})_2\text{Cl}_2$ after drying at 110° . Results are given in Table 2. Similarly, Rh(III) was

TABLE 2

(a) SEPARATION OF RHODIUM AND PLATINUM

Rh(III) taken = 9.11 mg

Pt(II) taken mg	Rh(III) found mg
10.32	9.07
10.32	9.04

(b) SEPARATION OF RHODIUM AND PALLADIUM

Rh(III) taken = 9.11 mg

Pd(II) taken mg	Rh(III) found mg	Pd(II) found mg
5.70	9.11	5.31
5.70	9.11	5.41
11.40	9.00	11.20
11.40	9.01	11.20

(c) SEPARATION OF RHODIUM AND OSMIUM

Rh(III) taken = 9.11 mg

Os(VIII) taken mg	Rh(III) found mg
5.00	9.11
5.00	9.00

separated from $\text{Os}_3(\text{VIII})$ by prior precipitation at pH 1.8-2.0 of osmium and estimation of rhodium in the filtrate as described above. The results are given in Table 2. The separations are rapid, clean and quantitative.

Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) which react with thiophene-2-aldoxime interfere in the estimation of rhodium.

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Studies of Complex Formation between 2-Hydroxy-5-Chloroacetophenone Oxime and Oxotitanium(IV)—Gravimetric Determination of Titanium

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AMONG few reagents employed for the estimation of titanium as its complex are 8-hydroxy quinoline^{1,2}, 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxy quinoline^{3,4} and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime^{5,6,7}. The main utility of this reagent over the well known methods is that the titanium chelate can be precipitated in a wide pH range and weighed directly after drying at 120-130°. The substitution of chlorine in the parent *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime increases the sensitivity and accuracy. The interference due to several ions has been removed by controlling the pH or by using suitable masking agents.

The reagent 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime form coloured precipitate with copper(II) (at pH 2.5-8.0), Ni(II) (pH 4.5-8.5), Co(II) (pH 5.0-9.0), Oxovanadium(IV) (pH 4.5-8.5). It has now been observed that titanium(IV) is quantitatively precipitated as a reddish yellow metal chelate $[\text{Ti}(\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{ClNO}_2]_2$ with this reagent in the pH range 3.5-8.5.

Materials and Methods

The reagent(HCAO) was prepared by Fries⁸ migration of *p*-chlorophenyl acetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. It was then converted into its oxime by refluxing it with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate. The product was recrystallised from ethanol(m.p. 185°). Reagent solution (0.5%) was prepared in 50% ethanol.

A weighed amount of potassium titanium oxalate(B. D. H.) was digested in conc. sulphuric

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acid and diluted with water titanium contents was estimated as TiO_2 .

Procedure :

A known volume of titanium(IV) solution (0.02M) was taken in a 400 ml beaker and diluted to 100 ml. An excess (twofold) of ethanolic solution of the reagent(0.5%) was added, followed by addition of acetic acid and ammonia buffer to adjust its pH(5.5-6.0). The complex was heated on a water bath at a temperature 60-70 for about 20 minutes, allowed to cool and filtered through a (G-4) sintered crucible. The precipitate was washed with water followed by 20% ethanol and dried at 120-130° to a constant weight. The results of estimations in the pH range 3.5-8.5 are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF TITANIUM(IV) IN THE pH RANGE 3.5-8.5

Sl. No.	pH of the soln	Amount of titanium taken = 11.82 mg		Error %
		Weight of titanium complex in mg	Titanium found in mg	
1.	3.0	Yellow colour	—	—
2.	3.5	65.2	11.76	-0.5
3.	4.0	65.4	11.79	-0.25
4.	4.5	65.4	11.79	-0.25
5.	5.5	65.4	11.79	-0.25
6.	6.5	65.6	11.88	+0.08
7.	7.5	65.4	11.79	-0.25
8.	8.0	65.4	11.79	-0.25
9.	8.5	65.2	11.76	-0.5

The results of 30 estimations of oxotitanium(IV) over a range of pH 4.5-8.0 revealed that 2 mg of titanium could be determined accurately; the conversion factor (titanium/titanium chelate) being 0.1804. The weighed amounts of titanium complex were ignited to titanium dioxide to estimate its titanium contents. It was found that the weights of TiO_2 correspond to calculated value within experimental error.

Effect of Foreign Ions on Precipitation of Titanium Complex :

The interference due to salts of foreign ions was removed in most of the cases by working at controlled pH values. Titanium has been determined satisfactorily at pH 3.8-4.0 in presence of about 2 times of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} and $B_4O_7^{2-}$, acetate, citrate and tartrate. The fluoride ions masked the titanium. Appreciable amounts (observations were taken 2-3 times) of some of the cations, e.g., Ni(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Th(IV) (yellow colour), Zr(IV), Mo(VI) (yellow colour) and $UO_2(II)$ (red colour) (at pH 3.5) could be tolerated. Cu(II), Fe(III) were masked by adding calculated amount of E.D.T.A. and tartrate respectively. Mg(II), Sr(II), Ca(II), Ba(II), Al(III) do not interfere in the precipitation of titanium.

Separation and Determination of Titanium(IV) and Cu(II) :

When titanium and copper were present in the binary mixture, copper was precipitated first at pH 2.5 with the reagent(HCAO). The mixture of the two ions was taken in a beaker (400 ml) and diluted to 100 ml. It is warmed to 35-40° and an excess (twofold) of the reagent solution was added with constant stirring. The buffcoloured precipitate was digested on a water bath at a temperature 70-80° for about half an hour, allowed to stand for two hours and filtered through a sintered crucible(G-4). The complex was washed with water, followed by 10% ethanol, dried at 110-120° and weighed as $Cu(C_8H_7ClNO_2)_2$. The conversion factor (copper/copper complex) is 0.1468.

The filtrate containing oxotitanium(IV) was evaporated to about 100 ml. Its pH was adjusted to 5.5 using acetic acid and ammonia buffer. The titanium was precipitated and determined as described above. The results are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION AND SEPARATION OF COPPER AND TITANIUM

Sl. No.	Metal taken in mg		Complex in mg		Metal found in mg		Error %	
	Cu	Ti	Cu	Ti	Cu	Ti	Cu	Ti
	1.	18.8	11.82	127.8	65.4	18.76	11.79	-0.21
2.	19.8	17.73	127.8	98.0	18.76	17.68	-0.21	-0.28
3.	31.5	17.73	214.2	98.0	31.44	17.68	-0.19	-0.28
4.	18.8	23.64	127.8	131.0	18.73	23.63	-0.21	-0.04
5.	31.5	11.82	214.2	65.2	31.44	11.73	-0.19	-0.5

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